

The Influence of Consumer Ethnocentrism and Perceived Quality on Repurchase Intention Through Attitude to Local Brands at NTB Mall

Rahmi Iryanti, Sulhaini, Handry Sudiartha Athar
Magister of Management, Faculty of Economics and Business
University of Mataram
Mataram, Indonesia

Abstract:- This research aims to examine the influence of consumer ethnocentrism and perceived quality on repurchase intentions through consumer attitudes toward local brands at NTB Mall. This type of research is causal associative research with a quantitative approach. Sampling was taken using a non-probability sampling technique, namely 100 respondents from NTB Mall consumers or customers. Data analysis used PLS-SEM techniques with Smart PLS 4 software. The results showed that consumer ethnocentrism and consumer attitudes had a significant positive effect on repurchase intentions, while perceived quality had a positive and insignificant effect on repurchase intentions. Consumer ethnocentrism has a positive and significant effect on consumer attitudes, while perceived quality has a positive and insignificant effect on consumer attitudes. In addition, consumer attitudes are able to mediate the influence of consumer ethnocentrism on repurchase intentions, but consumer attitudes are not able to mediate the influence of perceived quality on repurchase intentions. NTB Mall managers can support this research and utilize the results to understand more about consumer behavior and develop more effective marketing strategies.

Keywords:- Consumer Ethnocentrism, Perceived Quality, Consumer Attitude, Repurchase Intention.

I. INTRODUCTION

MSME activities are one of the activities that can create employment for the surrounding environment. MSMEs can also increase provincial income. For this reason, the government is making various efforts to increase the number of MSMEs in each region (Widjaja et al. 2018). Regarding the existence of MSMEs in Indonesia, every year the number of MSMEs continues to increase significantly, especially in West Nusa Tenggara Province. Based on One NTB Data for 2023, the number of MSMEs increased rapidly from 2019 to 2022, from 48,091 MSMEs to 193,743 MSMEs. This shows that there is very rapid economic growth and is a promising business opportunity, as well as the support of the local community and government.

Along with the development of increasingly sophisticated technology, system changes are encouraged. One of them is the trading and transaction system, which is usually carried out

offline (directly) is now developing online (indirectly) (Aeda, 2022). E-commerce is a new business strategy that can improve the quality of products and services, as well as improve the level of service provision while linking the requirements of organizations, (online) suppliers, and consumers towards reducing costs (Shaw, Michael, 2012). The e-commerce business in Indonesia continues to grow, not only helping to meet consumer needs but also becoming a bridge for MSMEs to be able to connect widely with potential customers.

According to Adekunle & Ejechi, (2018), repurchase intention is when consumers start making efforts to buy the same brand, product or service again. Apart from that, according to Thongkruer & Wanarat, (2020), repeat purchases are an opportunity that someone will continue to enjoy products or services from a particular brand in the future. Zeithaml et al. (1996) have suggested two types of positive repurchase intentions: first, intention to repurchase and second, intention to engage in positive word of mouth and recommend. RI is the result of customer attitudes towards the performance of the services consumed. One construct that has received attention is value. The indicators for measuring repurchase intention are attitude towards the product, attitude towards advertising, and attitude towards interest (Huang et al. 2004).

Consumer interest is strongly influenced by the characteristics of the product selection on the benefits of a product (Yani et al. 2022). Purchase intention is part of the consumer behavior component in consumption attitudes, the respondent's tendency to act before the purchase decision is implemented (Kinneer & Taylor, 1995). According to Tjiptono & Craig-Less (2004), one of the variables that influence interest in purchasing local brands is ethnocentrism. Consumers can develop ethnocentrism, namely an attitude that views purchasing imported goods negatively and is prouder of homemade products. They believe that buying imported products can harm the national economy, cause unemployment, and is unpatriotic. Tjiptono (2005) stated that the more ethnocentrism a consumer is, the more interested they are in buying local brands. Apart from how consumers have ethnocentrism towards a product, there is a need for an attitude of perceived quality towards a product because according to (Graciola et al. 2018). customers who have information about prices can have higher or lower price sensitivity. Palazzo et al. (2021) stated that an approach from the consumer's perspective is something that can be used to measure whether the quality

presented is as expected or not. This statement is in line with Zeithaml's (1998) definition of perceived quality, which states that perceived quality is a customer's assessment of the overall quality or superiority of the product. So, the higher perceived quality can make interaction with a brand more positive (Marques et al. 2020).

Consumer ethnocentrism is a belief held by consumers about the suitability and morality of purchasing products from abroad (Shimp and Sharma, 1987: 280). It is expected that those with higher ethnocentric tendencies believe that purchasing domestic products is more moral and appropriate and vice versa for products originating from abroad. Thus, Shimp (1984), who first discussed the concept, pointed out that buying foreign-made products harms the domestic economy, causes people to lose their jobs, and is inconsistent with patriotic thinking and the belief that domestic products are superior to products from the country. Other. Several previous studies stated that consumers' high level of love for their culture will result in the emergence of ethnocentrism. Krystalis et al. (2007) in Miguel et al. (2022) stated that consumer ethnocentrism influences consumer preferences and attitudes toward an item. Consumers think that local products can be used as an option compared to international products. Aldewahab et al. (2020) define ethnocentrism as a self-defense mechanism used by local communities, governments and individuals to protect their economy from attacks by opposing parties.

The explanation above can be supported by previous research conducted by Udayani et al. (2018), Febriyana, (2018) which states that consumer ethnocentrism has a positive effect on repurchase intention. Meanwhile, Larasati et al. 2021 states that consumer ethnocentrism does not affect repurchase intention. The differences in the results of this study indicate that there is still inconsistency in the research results, so further research needs to be carried out. The indicators for measuring consumer ethnocentrism according to Shimp and Sharma, (1987) are the origin of the product, concern for the country, and feelings of reluctance to buy products from outside the original region.

Perceived quality according to Aaker, (2007) is the customer's perception of the quality of products and services related to predetermined goals. Consumer perception appears to be a comparison between consumer satisfaction with a product and other products. Customers consider perceived quality to be a more specific concept based on product and service features. Companies can have a degree of control over quality. Thus, it is suggested that when perceived quality is considered as an overall assessment, then perceived quality is understood as a source of satisfaction (Llusar et al. 2001). The same thing was also conveyed in research by Wijaksono and Ali (2019), which published that the higher the view of quality in the mind of each buyer, the greater the customer's intention and willingness to make repeated purchases of the company's products continuously.

Yulianti & Maemunah, (2023) support this argument that perceived quality has a significant effect on repurchase intention. Meanwhile, Gunawan (2021) obtained different results that perceived quality had no effect on repurchase intention. There are still research gaps found in previous research, so it is necessary to carry out further research regarding these variables. The indicators for measuring perceived quality according to Gupta, (2014) are product usability, product variety, and interest in the product.

Consumer confidence and choice of a brand is a consumer attitude. In many cases, attitudes towards a particular brand will influence whether consumers buy or not. It is stated that attitude is the most special and much-needed concept in contemporary social psychology, so it can be said that attitude is one of the most important concepts for marketers to understand consumers. Chusna & Riptiana, 2021. The initial definition of attitude was put forward by Thurstone (in Azwar, 1988), he saw attitude as a fairly simple concept, namely the amount of influence a person has over or against an object. Meng and Choi (2019) in Abbasi et al. (2020) defines attitude as a function of a person's beliefs which can be formed from second-party information, various information processing processes, or observation. Ajzen (1985) revealed a strong connection between attitudes, habits, and intentions. Vera-Martinez et al. (2022) in Arachchi, (2022) revealed that consumer awareness of quality can influence consumer attitudes toward a product or service. Furthermore, this attitude will influence consumers repurchase intentions for a product.

Supported by previous research that attitude influences repurchase intention by Pangestoe & Purwianti, (2022) and Haiban & Rimadiaz, (2023) that attitude has a significant influence on repurchase intention. Bag et al. (2019) explains the indicators used to measure the influence of these variables on the desire to pay back, the desire to use the product sustainably, and the desire to buy the product.

The NTB Mall website is a market place application that facilitates marketing activities for MSME players. There are 212 MSMEs registered to join NTB Mall Offline with more than 1,300 variants of selected products. Meanwhile, in the application, it has been recorded that 1,250 MSMEs and more than 7,200 products have been input into the application system. Data from NTB Mall from 2022 to 2023 has recorded more than 4,326 consumers both online and offline and more than 2,500 consumers visited and purchased products more than twice online and offline at NTB Mall. Based on existing conditions, researchers want to dig deeper into how innovations carried out by MSMEs and NTB MALL make consumers or the public like and become a need for the local products being marketed. Researchers want to focus on whether love for local products or in terms of quality that is able to satisfy consumers is a factor in consumers' intentions to repurchase or repurchase at NTB Mall, either through the application (online) or coming directly to the shop (offline).

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. *The Planned Behavior Theory*

Ajzen (1985) expressed The Planned Behavior Theory (TPB) as an intention that arises from within a person due to the influence of consumer attitudes toward certain habits, personal values, and perceptions of habitual control. George (2004) stated that TPB is associated with personal feelings related to habits. Ajzen (2002) stated that a person's control habits do not involve habits that indicate a particular behavior. But this shows the steps a person takes regarding controlling behavior. Ajzen (2002) also stated that intention is one of the variables that underlie behavior.

B. *Repurchase Intention*

Chaudhuri & Holbrook (2001) revealed that trust in a brand is an important factor that influences consumer's repurchase intention. Consumers will tend to repurchase a product because a sense of confidence arises in consumers if the product is able to fulfill their expectations. Hur et al. (2011) stated that trust creates a sense of security and protection in consumers. Then this trust will influence the consumer's repurchase intention. Casalo (2007) stated that consumer trust is associated with a positive brand image. This brand image will then make consumers want to repurchase a product in the future. Another opinion from Spears & Singh (2004) states that repurchase intention is a consumer's conscious plan to purchase a product again in the future.

C. *Consumer Ethnocentrism*

Summer (1906) in Aldewahab et al. (2020) define ethnocentrism as the view that one group can be central to everything. And other things outside the group will be measured and weighed based on the preferences of that group. Jacobi (2018), stated that someone who has an ethnocentric attitude will assume that his group has a higher level than other groups. Siamagka & Balabanis (2015), define ethnocentrism as a self-defense mechanism used by local communities, governments and individuals to protect their economy from attacks by opposing parties. Sulhaini & Mulyono, (2014) cite that consumer ethnocentrism is consumer perception of local and foreign products. Local and foreign products are very dependent on consumers' feelings towards their own country (Notari et al. 2011). Shimp & Sharma (1987), revealed ethnocentrism as a belief associated with a moral attitude towards purchasing foreign products.

D. *Perceived Quality*

Chowdhary & Prakas (2007) revealed that the company's orientation is to achieve a certain level of quality. Ojalaso (2019), stated that an approach from the consumer's perspective is something that can be used to measure whether the quality presented is as expected or not. Kotler and Armstrong (20017), stated that consumers and service providers are two parties who have an important role related to creating the concept of quality. Parasuraman et al. (1994), stated that finding two views of quality from consumers and producers is difficult to do. Therefore, it is necessary to develop good relations between the two parties. Parasuraman et al. (1994) further stated that maximum quality conditions can be achieved only when

mutually beneficial conditions are created between producers and consumers.

E. *Consumer Attitude*

MacKenzie & Lutz (1989), stated that advertising credibility, advertising perception, attitudes towards advertisers, and consumers' moods are things that influence advertising success. Droge (1989), revealed that consumer attitudes towards a product can influence consumer purchasing intentions in the future. Anridho and Liao (2013), stated that advertising will influence consumer attitudes towards a product. Soudien et al. (2017), stated that consumers' feelings can influence the attitudes they will take regarding certain products.

F. *The Influence of Consumer Ethnocentrism on Repurchase Intention*

Lesakova (2016) in Aldewahab et al. (2020) stated that this ethnocentrism attitude can be a consideration that influences consumer purchasing decisions. Lee and Mazodier (2015) in Aldewahab et al. (2020) revealed that ethnocentric attitudes can have a negative influence on decisions to purchase foreign products. Balbanis (2004) in Aldewahab et al. (2020) stated that ethnocentrism behavior is more suitable for measuring bias toward purchasing local products compared to measuring rejection of foreign products. This will cause consumers to avoid repeat purchases of products originating from outside their region. Firbasova (2003) in Miguel et al. (2022) stated that consumers who adhere to ethnocentrism will tend to choose local products over products originating from other countries, even though there is no clear reason for this choice. The basis for choosing products from ethnocentric consumers arises from their understanding that products from the same country as the consumer originates from have better quality compared to products from other countries. This is worthy of attention for companies because consumers will tend to repurchase products from the same country of origin as where they live, compared to repurchasing products originating from outside the area where they live.

H1: Consumer ethnocentrism has a positive effect on repurchase intention.

G. *The Influence of Perceived Quality on Repurchase Intention*

Bagri (2015) in Palazzo et al. (2021) revealed that the quality of a product or service contains what consumers expect the producer to fulfill. Mesala and Paul (2018) in Palazzo et al. (2021) stated that in fulfilling quality, companies are not only expected to fulfill what consumers want. But companies are also expected to provide solutions to problems faced by consumers regarding the products or services offered. Gupta (2014) in Palazzo et al. (2021) stated that the perception of consumer quality that can be fulfilled by the company will lead to consumer satisfaction. Furthermore, this satisfaction will lead to repeat purchase intentions.

Gronroos (1988) in Palazzo et al. (2021) stated that if there is trust in consumers because their perception of quality is met, this can lead to repeat purchase intentions. Eisengerich and Eric (2008) in Palazzo et al. (2021) stated that if companies want to improve their performance, they must be able to meet

consumers' quality perceptions. This is because consumers will tend to make repeat purchases if they are sure that the product offered is a quality product and meets their expectations. Parasuraman et al. (2006) in Garcia et al. (2020) revealed that the quality of service provided has a big impact on loyalty, positive word of mouth, and repeat purchase intentions.

H2: Perceived quality has a positive effect on repurchase intention.

H. The Influence of Attitude on Repurchase Intention

Attitudes towards a brand can also be formed through a person's basic beliefs about the extrinsic attributes of a brand and the symbolic benefits contained in it (Lutz, 1975; Keller, 1998). If someone has a pleasant (positive) attitude towards a particular object or brand, then he will help, pay attention, and do something, for example by making a purchase. On the other hand, if someone has an unpleasant (negative) attitude towards an object or brand, then he will criticize it and do something that is detrimental to the object (Hawkins et al. 1992:354). Based on research conducted by Wijaya (2014), also shows that a consumer's positive attitude toward a brand can increase the consumer's repurchase intention or the product. This happens when consumers feel satisfied with the products/services they receive from a company providing these goods/services, there is a very big possibility for consumers to make repeat purchases. Based on this explanation, the hypothesis to be tested is as follows:

H3: Attitude has a positive effect on repurchase intention.

I. The Influence of Consumer Ethnocentrism on Attitudes

Chusna & Riptino, (2021) explained that the more a person has a tendency toward ethnocentrism towards a product, the more positive consumer attitudes towards that product will emerge. Consumers who tend to be ethnocentric tend to have the perception that products or services from their own ethnic group are of better quality or more appropriate to their needs. They may believe that the product or service was designed with the values and preferences of their ethnic group in mind. This perception can influence an individual's attitude towards a product or service, by producing a positive attitude based on the belief that the product or service is better than others. The results of this research are in line with research conducted by Novita (2017) which states that consumer ethnocentrism has a positive and significant effect on consumer attitudes towards local products.

H4: Consumer ethnocentrism has a positive effect on consumer attitudes

J. The Influence of Perceived Quality on Attitudes

When consumers have a high perception of the quality of a product or service, they tend to have a positive attitude towards the product or service. Perceptions of high quality can include aspects such as reliability, performance, design, materials, and value of the product or service. If consumers believe that the product or service is of good quality, they will tend to have a positive attitude towards it. This positive attitude can form a desire to purchase, recommend, and maintain a relationship with the product or service. Part of consumers' perceptions of the overall quality of a brand conceptualizes consumers' attitudes and evaluations about the merits of a

product. Assael (2001) stated that attitude towards a brand is a mental statement of the message recipient who evaluates the positive or negative, good or bad, like or dislike, quality or poor quality of a product. Aaker & Keller (1990) explained that the relationship between perceived quality and consumer attitudes towards it tends to be positive only shown by the existence of fit between the original product and the expanded product. If the brand is associated with high quality, this expansion will be profitable, but if it is associated with low quality, the expansion will actually be detrimental to Herlina & Khoiriah, (2010).

H5: Perceived quality has a positive effect on consumer attitudes

K. The Influence of Consumer Ethnocentrism on Repurchase Intention Through Consumer Attitudes

Chusna & Riptino, (2021) explain that the more a person has a tendency toward ethnocentrism towards a product, the more positive consumer attitudes towards that product will emerge. Consumers who tend to be ethnocentric tend to have the perception that products or services from their own ethnic group are of better quality or better suited to their needs. They may believe that the product or service was designed with the values and preferences of their ethnic group in mind. Meanwhile, attitudes towards brands can also be formed through a person's basic beliefs about the extrinsic attributes of a brand and also the symbolic benefits contained in it (Lutz, 1975; Keller, 1998). If someone has a pleasant (positive) attitude towards a particular object or brand, then he will help, pay attention and do something, for example by making a purchase. On the other hand, if someone has an unpleasant (negative) attitude towards an object or brand, then he will criticize it and do something that is detrimental to the object (Hawkins et al. 1992:354).

H6: Consumer ethnocentrism on repurchase intention can be mediated by consumer attitudes

L. The Influence of Perceived Quality on Repurchase Intention Through Consumer Attitudes

Assael (2001) stated that attitude towards a brand is a mental statement of the message recipient who evaluates the positive or negative, good or bad, like or dislike, quality or poor quality of a product. Aaker & Keller (1990) explained that the relationship between perceived quality and consumer attitudes towards it tends to be positive only shown by the existence of fit between the original product and the expanded product. If the brand is associated with high quality, this expansion will be profitable, but if it is associated with low quality, the expansion will actually be detrimental to Herlina & Khoiriah, (2010). Meanwhile, attitudes towards brands can also be formed through a person's basic beliefs about the extrinsic attributes of a brand and also the symbolic benefits contained in it (Lutz, 1975; Keller, 1998). If someone has a pleasant (positive) attitude towards a particular object or brand, then he will help, pay attention and do something, for example by making a purchase. On the other hand, if someone has an unpleasant (negative) attitude towards an object or brand, then he will criticize it and do something that is detrimental to the object (Hawkins et al. 1992:354).

H7: Perceived quality on repurchase intention can be mediated by consumer attitudes

III. RESEARCH METHOD

This research data was collected using Google Forms, an online questionnaire application. Respondents came from diverse demographics regarding gender, age, educational background, occupation, and place of origin. The sampling technique used was non-probability sampling, and then the questionnaire was distributed to 100 respondents from NTB Mall’s customers. Data analysis in this study used a variance-based structural equation test with the partial Least Square (PLS) SEM method using smart PLS 4.0 software. The choice

of the PLS method in this research is based on the data characteristics of the SEM-PLS model which can test and identify with a low error rate even with a relatively small sample size.

Characteristics of respondents, this study collected responses from 120 respondents, because it uses an online questionnaire form, all questions can be mandatory so that respondents answer all questions can be mandatory so that all respondents answer all questions asked. The following characteristics of respondents varied greatly in this study:

Table 1. Characteristics of respondents

Items	Classifications	Number of People	Percentage (%)
Gender	Man	63	52.5
	Woman	57	47.5
Ages	18-22	21	21%
	23-28	46	46%
	29-34	15	15%
	> 34	18	18%
Job	ASN	38	38%
	Private Employee	24	24%
	Entrepreneur	6	6%
	Student	25	25%
	Housewife	4	4%
	Honorary	3	3%
Education	High School	19	19%
	DIII	5	5%
	DIV	2	2%
	S1	72	72%
	S2	2	2%
Place of Origin	NTB	77	77%
	Outside NTB	23	23%

The results of the item reliability test are presented in the table. It can be seen from the table that all indicators of this research variable have factor loading values greater than 0.70 (Hair, 2010). All items are said to be valid and used to test this research model.

Based on this table, all measurement items on each variable, both consumer ethnocentrism, perceived quality, repurchase intention and consumer attitudes, show an outer loading value > 0.5, so it can be said that all indicators used are valid.

Table 2. Convergent Validity Test Result

Variable	Item	Outer Loadings	Ket
<i>Consumer Ethnocentrism (X1)</i>	Locals should only buy products that are made in their home region.	0,763	Valid
	Locally made products are number one.	0,803	Valid
	Buying local is the best decision	0,813	Valid
	Purchase of products from outside the region should be minimized unless the product is really needed.	0,941	Valid
	Buying locally made products means helping the local economy.	0,927	Valid
	Buying products made in other regions is wrong because it can reduce regional income	0,918	Valid
	A true local should always buy products made in their home region.	0,920	Valid
	Residents should not buy products from outside the region as it can harm the original region and lead to unemployment.	0,902	Valid
	It may be costly in the long run, but I will keep buying local products no matter what.	0,865	Valid
	Residents from outside the region may not sell their products outside the region of origin.	0,874	Valid
	Products from outside the original region should be subject to high fines.	0,702	Valid
	The out-of-region products that we buy should be products that are not available in the area of origin.	0,705	Valid

<i>Perceived Quality</i> (X2)	Products sold at NTB Mall can be used properly	0,803	Valid
	Products sold at NTB Mall are of good quality	0,941	Valid
	Products sold at NTB Mall are well packaged	0,900	Valid
	I received NTB Mall products in good condition	0,961	Valid
	The products offered at NTB Mall to consumers are very diverse	0,965	Valid
	The products offered at NTB Mall make me interested in buying them	0,963	Valid
Sikap Konsumen (Z)	I feel that if the product provider is an MSME entrepreneur who has expertise	0,937	Valid
	I feel that if the product provider is an MSME entrepreneur who has experience	0,901	Valid
	I feel that if the product provider is an MSME entrepreneur who has the knowledge	0,836	Valid
	I feel that the product provider is a quality MSME entrepreneur	0,933	Valid
	I feel that the product provider is an MSME entrepreneur who has expertise	0,937	Valid
	I feel that the advertisement of the product offered is a good advertisement	0,898	Valid
	I feel that the advertisements of the products offered annoy me.	0,907	Valid
	I like advertisements that are made to offer existing products	0,894	Valid
	I feel that the advertisement made to offer the product is an attractive advertisement	0,813	Valid
	I feel that the brand of MSME products that are marketed is a good brand	0,819	Valid
	I feel that the existing MSME product brands are quality brands	0,825	Valid
	I really like the brand of MSME products offered	0,819	Valid
	I am happy with the brand of MSME products offered	0,824	Valid
	<i>Repurchase Intention</i> (Y)	I want to pay back for the MSME products offered	0,950
I will buy MSME products again in the future		0,956	Valid
I have the intention to continue using MSME products		0,939	Valid
I choose to buy products made by MSMEs over those made by other companies.		0,764	Valid

IV. RESULTS

This research uses a Partial Least Square (PLS) analysis approach to test the research hypothesis that was stated previously. Hypothesis testing can be done through t-statistic values and probability values through Bootstrapping which can be seen in the following figure:

Fig 1. Path Coefficient

Table 4. Hypothesis Test Results

Relations	Coefficients	T Statistic	P Value	
<i>Consumer Ethnocentrism -> Repurchase Intention</i>	0,253	2,463	0,014	Positive and Significant
<i>Perceived Quality -> Repurchase Intention</i>	0,077	0,959	0,338	Positive and Not Significant
<i>Sikap -> Repurchase Intention</i>	0,466	4,911	0,000	Positive and Significant
<i>Consumer Ethnocentrism -> Sikap</i>	0,100	1,048	0,295	Positive and NoT Significant
<i>Perceived Quality -> Sikap</i>	0,247	2,165	0,031	Positive and Significant
<i>Consumer Ethnocentrism -> Sikap -> Repurchase Intention</i>	0,047	0,924	0,356	Positive and Not Significant
<i>Perceived Quality -> Sikap -> Repurchase Intention</i>	0,115	2,045	0,041	Positive and Significant

V. DISCUSSION

The path coefficient shows a coefficient value of 0.253, a t-statistic value of 2.463 > 1.96, and a P value of 0.014 < 0.05. So the first hypothesis (H1) is accepted. This means that consumer ethnocentrism has a significant positive effect on repurchase intention. This means that if consumers have an attitude or tendency to support local products or prioritize purchasing domestic products, they tend to have a higher intention to buy these products again at NTB Mall. Consumers who have an ethnocentric attitude play an important role in consuming domestically made products and contribute little to the consumption of imported products (Febriyan, 2018). Good product quality and a positive shopping experience can trigger the intention to return to shopping (repurchase intention). In line with the Theory of Planned Behavior through subjective norms. Subjective norms reflect individuals' perceptions of the expectations of the people closest to them in their lives regarding certain behaviors. In the context of consumer ethnocentrism, subjective norms reflect individuals' perceptions of the extent to which they feel pressure or expectation to repurchase products or services from their ethnic group. The results of this research are in line with previous research conducted by Udayani et al. (2018); Febriyan, (2018); Yani et al, (2022) which shows the results that consumer ethnocentrism has a positive and significant effect on repurchase intention

The path coefficient shows a coefficient value of 0.077, a t-statistic value of 0.959 < 1.96, and a P value of 0.338 > 0.05. So the second hypothesis (H2) is rejected. This means that perceived quality has a positive and insignificant effect on repurchase intention. This means that the perception of product quality does not influence the interest in repurchasing products marketed at NTB Mall. This can happen because of several possibilities, such as customers not getting the perceived quality, or not getting what they expect or want from the products sold at NTB Mall when they buy the product during their first transaction, so they feel disappointed and automatically will not buy it. repurchase intention (Islamy et al., 2023). This research is in line with research conducted by Hsu et al (2014: 241) which states that perceived quality does not have a significant effect on repurchase intention because their research states that consumers cannot feel the quality of the products offered as seen from the many competitors offering similar products or consumers have not discovered uniqueness (Tuinesia et al., 2022). One of the factors in the success of customers making repurchase intentions is that if customers can receive positive value from a product, they will

tend to make repurchase intentions (Liao et al., 2012). In line with research conducted by Gunawan (2021), perceived quality does not have a significant effect on the decision to repurchase a product.

The path coefficient shows a coefficient value of 0.466, a t-statistic value of 04.911 < 1.96, and a P value of 0.000 > 0.05. So the third hypothesis (H3) is accepted. This means that consumer attitudes have a positive and significant effect on repurchase intention. This means that the more positive a consumer's attitude is towards a product or brand, the higher their intention to make a repeat purchase or shop again at NTB Mall. Attitude is a comprehensive assessment that reflects a person's feelings of liking or disliking an object or event. This is in line with Han, Hsu, and Sheu (2009) who stated that a person's attitudes and beliefs are significantly related to and influence the choice of whether or not to buy a product or service. According to Sukhu and Scharff (2016), consumer trust will have a positive impact on consumer loyalty which can have a positive effect on consumer repurchase interest. This is also supported by research by Kang, Tang, and Bosselman (2011) which states that positive consumer attitudes can increase consumer interest in buying again. Each individual's attitude will be different depending on the size of the stimulus that influences them. If someone has a positive attitude towards a product, that person will try to get the product they want, making it difficult to switch to another product (Sudarti & Ulum, 2019).

The path coefficient shows a coefficient value of 0.100, a t statistic value of 1.048 < 1.96, and a P value of 0.295 > 0.05. So the fourth hypothesis (H4) is rejected. This means that consumer ethnocentrism has a positive and insignificant effect on consumer attitudes. This means that sentiments or attitudes that support local or domestic products (consumer ethnocentrism) do not have a significant impact on consumer attitudes toward the products offered at NTB Mall. The more a person has a tendency towards ethnocentrism towards local products, the more positive consumer attitudes towards these local products will emerge (Chusna & Riptiono, 2021). This will influence consumer attitudes towards supporting local products marketed at NTB Mall. The results of this research are in line with those conducted by Sumiati (2019), that consumer ethnocentrism has a positive and insignificant effect on consumer attitudes.

The path coefficient shows a coefficient value of 0.247, a t-statistic value of $2.165 > 1.96$, and a P value of $0.031 < 0.05$. So the fifth hypothesis (H5) is accepted. This means that perceived quality has a positive and significant effect on consumer attitudes. This means that the higher the perception of product or service quality by consumers, the higher their attitude towards the product, brand, or place to shop at NTB Mall. Quality is an important factor in shopping decisions. Consumers often look for quality products that can meet their needs well. When consumers feel that local products are a quality choice, they tend to have a positive attitude toward the product (Saputra et al. 2017). High-quality perceptions of local products can increase consumer confidence in these products (Septian & Hendarwati, 2021). When consumers feel that local products are good quality, they tend to have a positive attitude toward the products at NTB Mall.

The path coefficient shows a coefficient value of 0.047, a t-statistic value of $0.924 < 1.96$, and a P value of $0.356 > 0.05$. So, the sixth hypothesis (H6) is rejected. This means that the influence of consumer ethnocentrism on repurchase intention cannot be through consumer attitudes. This means that, although there may be an influence of consumer ethnocentrism on repurchase intention (perhaps directly or through other factors), this relationship is not related to consumer attitudes towards certain products or brands. In other words, consumer attitudes towards local products do not play a role in the relationship between ethnocentrism sentiment and the intention to shop for local products again. The influence of consumer ethnocentrism on repurchase intention does not depend on consumer attitudes toward local products. In other words, consumers may have strong ethnocentrism sentiments, which directly influence their intention to make repeat purchases, without passing through positive or negative attitudes towards local products.

The path coefficients show a coefficient value of 0.115, a t-statistic value of $2.045 < 1.96$, and a P value of $0.041 < 0.05$. So, the sixth hypothesis (H7) is accepted. This means that the influence of perceived quality on repurchase intention can be through consumer attitudes. This means that the relationship between perceived product quality and repurchase intention is influenced by the extent to which consumers have a positive attitude toward the product. Perceived product quality is the main factor influencing consumers' shopping decisions, and in the case of local products at NTB Mall, it is important to understand its relationship with consumers' intention to shop again. Research shows that when consumers have positive perceptions about the quality of local products they buy at NTB Mall, they are more likely to have a positive attitude towards those products. This positive consumer attitude reflects their satisfaction with the product, confidence in its quality, and a strong preference for local products. This positive attitude in turn encourages consumers' intention to make repeat purchases.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of statistical analysis in this research, it is hoped that it can fill the research gap in previous studies that have been identified where consumer ethnocentrism has a significant positive effect on repurchase intention, with consumers having an attitude of prioritizing purchasing domestic products, they tend to have higher intentions to buy the product again at NTB Mall. Perceived quality has a positive and insignificant effect on repurchase intention, perceived product quality does not affect the intention to repurchase products marketed at NTB Mall. Consumer attitude has a positive and significant effect on repurchase intention. The more positive the consumer's attitude is towards the product or brand, the higher their intention to repurchase or shop again at NTB Mall. Then consumer ethnocentrism has a positive and insignificant effect on consumer attitudes, sentiment does not have a significant impact on consumer attitudes towards the products offered at NTB Mall. Furthermore, perceived quality has a positive and significant effect on consumer attitudes. The higher the perception of product or service quality by consumers, the higher their attitude towards the products and brands at NTB Mall. Consumer ethnocentrism on repurchase intention cannot be through consumer attitudes, although there may be an influence of consumer ethnocentrism on repurchase intention (perhaps directly or through other factors). However, perceived quality on repurchase intention can be through consumer attitudes, the relationship between perceived product quality and repurchase intention is influenced by the extent to which consumers have a positive attitude towards the product marketed at NTB Mall.

The managerial implications of this study are NTB Mall managers can develop campaigns that emphasize the value of local products and how purchasing them supports the local economy and community. Although perceived quality does not have a significant effect on repurchase intention, it still has a positive impact. This means it is important to continue to improve the quality of products and services at NTB Mall. NTB Mall managers can support this research and utilize the results to better understand consumer behavior and develop more effective marketing strategies.

The measurement of consumer attitudes in this study may have limitations, especially related to the subjectivity and complexity of the concept of consumer attitudes. Future research can explore more deeply the factors that influence consumer attitudes

REFERENCES

- [1]. Abbasi, G. A., Kumaravelu, J., Goh, Y. N., & Dara Singh, K. S. (2021). Understanding the intention to revisit a destination by expanding the theory of planned behaviour (TPB). *Spanish Journal of Marketing - ESIC*, 25(2), 282–311. <https://doi.org/10.1108/SJME-12-2019-0109>
- [2]. Abdelwahab, D., Jiménez, N. H., San-Martín, S., & Prodanova, J. (2020). Between love and boycott: a story of dual origin brands. *Spanish Journal of Marketing - ESIC*, 24(3), 377–402. <https://doi.org/10.1108/SJME-12-2019-0105>
- [3]. Adekunle, S.A. and Ejechi, J.O. (2018), "Modelling repurchase intention among smartphones users in Nigeria", *Journal of Modelling in Management*, Vol. 13 No. 4, pp. 794-814. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JM2-12-2017-0138>
- [4]. Ajzen, I. 1985. From Intentions to Actions: A Theory of Planned Behavior. In J. Kuhl and J. Beckman (Eds.), *Action-Control: From Cognition to Behavior* (hal. 11-39). Heidelberg: Springer.
- [5]. Ajzen, I. 1991. The Theory of Planned Behavior. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 50: 179-211.
- [6]. Ajzen, I. (2002). Perceived Behavioral Control, Self-Efficacy, Locus of Control, and The Theory of Planned Behavior. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes* 50, 179-211.
- [7]. Azwar, S. (1988). *Sikap manusia, teori, dan pengukurannya*. Yogyakarta: Penerbit Liberty.
- [8]. Casaló Ariño, Luis & Flavian, Carlos & Guinalú, Miguel. (2007). The Influence of Satisfaction, Perceived Reputation and Trust on a Consumer's Commitment to a Website. *Journal of Marketing Communications*. 13. 1-17. [10.1080/13527260600951633](https://doi.org/10.1080/13527260600951633).
- [9]. Chaudhuri, A., & Holbrook, M. B. (2001). The chain of effects from brand trust and brand affect to brand performance: The role of brand loyalty. *Journal of Marketing*, 65(2), 81–93. <https://doi.org/10.1509/jmkg.65.2.81.18255>
- [10]. Chowdhary, Nimit & Prakash, Monika. (2007). Prioritizing service quality dimensions. *Managing Service Quality*. 17. 493-509. [10.1108/09604520710817325](https://doi.org/10.1108/09604520710817325).
- [11]. Chusna, A., & Riptiono, S. (2021). Pengaruh Consumer Ethnocentrism Tendency, Persepsi Nilai dan Atribut Produk Terhadap Niat Beli dengan Sikap Konsumen sebagai Variabel Intervening. *Jurnal Ilmiah Mahasiswa Manajemen, Bisnis Dan Akuntansi (JIMMBA)*, 3(1), 57-77. <https://doi.org/10.32639/jimmba.v3i1.779>
- [12]. Febryan, Michael Gebi. (2018). Pengaruh Ethnosentrisme Konsumen, Product Knowledge dan Perceived Quality Terhadap Minat Beli Ulang Produk Sepatu Impor Adidas di Salatiga. <https://repository.uksw.edu/handle/123456789/23762>
- [13]. George, J. F. 2004. The Theory of Planned Behavior and Internet Purchasing. *Internet Research* Vol. 14 No. 3 hal 198—212.
- [14]. Gupta, Anjali. 2014. E-Commerce: Role Of E-Commerce In Today's Business. *International Journal of Computing and Corporate Research* Volume 4
- [15]. Haiban, Muhammad Luthfi and Rimadias, Santi (2023) Analysis of Factors Forming Attitude towards Brand and Repurchase Intention by Using Brand Ambassadors on the Shopee Online Shopping Platform. *Jurnal Ilmu Manajemen dan Ekonomika*, 15 (2). pp. 41-56.
- [16]. Huang, Jen-Hung., Bruce C.Y. Lee, dan S.H. Ho. 2004. "Consumer Attitude Toward Gray Market Goods". *International Marketing Review* 21(6): 598 -614
- [17]. Hur, Youngjin., Yong Jae Ko., & Joseph Valacich. 2011. 'A Structural Model of the Relationships Between Sport Website Quality, ESatisfaction, and E-Loyalty. *Journal of Sport Management*. 25, 458-473.
- [18]. Khan et al., 2019. Celebrity Endorsement and Purchase Intentions: The Role of Perceived Quality and Brand Loyalty. *Market Forces College of Management Sciences*. Volume 14, Issue 2. December 2019.
- [19]. Kinnear, Thomas C, Dan Taylor, James R., (1995). *Riset Pemasaran, Edisi Tiga*, Jakarta: Erlangga.
- [20]. Kotler dan Keller. 2014. *Buku Prinsip Prinsip Pemasaran By Philip Kotler Gary Armstrong Edisi 12 Jilid I&2. Edisi Ke 13*. Jakarta: Erlangga.
- [21]. Krystallis, A., Chrysochoidis, G. and Scholderer, J. (2007), "Consumer-perceived quality in 'traditional' food chains: the case of the Greek meat supply chain", *Appetite*, Vol. 48 No. 1, pp. 54-68, doi: [10.1016/j.appet.2006.06.003](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.appet.2006.06.003).
- [22]. Kurniawan, A., Lukitaningsih, A., & Hutami, L. T. (2023). Pengaruh Kualitas Makanan, Store Atmosphere Terhadap Loyalitas Konsumen Dengan Kepuasan Konsumen Sebagai Variabel Intervening. *Jurnal Ekonomi Keuangan Dan Bisnis Syaiah*, 5.
- [23]. Llusar et al. 2001. Measuring the Relationship between Firm Perceived Quality and Customer Satisfaction and Its Influence on Purchase Intentions. *Total Quality Management*. 12 (6) : 719 – 734.
- [24]. Marques, C., da Silva, R. V., Davcik, N. S., & Faria, R. T. (2020). The Role of Brand Equity in a New Rebranding Strategy of a Private Label Brand. *Journal of Business Research*, 117(June), 497–507. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2020.06.022>
- [25]. Miguel, L., Marques, S., & Duarte, A. P. (2022). The influence of consumer ethnocentrism on purchase of domestic fruits and vegetables: application of the extended theory of planned behaviour. *British Food Journal*, 124(13), 599–618. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BFJ-11-2021-1208>
- [26]. Palazzo, M., Foroudi, P., & Ferri, M. A. (2021). Examining antecedents and consequences of perceived service quality in the hotel industry: a comparison between London and New York. *TQM Journal*, 33(7), 193–221. <https://doi.org/10.1108/TQM-09-2020-0203>
- [27]. Pangestoe, J., & Purwianti. (2022). Analisa Pengaruh Citra merek , Selebgram , Sikap , Kepercayaan konsumen, dan Kesadaran merek terhadap Niat beli Pada Fashion Sportwear di Kota Batam. *SEIKO (Jurnal of Management and Business*, 5(1), 137–155.

- [28]. Shimp, T. A., & Sharma, S. (1987). Consumer Validation Construction Ethnocentrism: of the. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 24(3), 280–289. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/3151638>.
- [29]. Siamagka, Nikoleta-Theofania & Balabanis, George. (2015). Revisiting Consumer Ethnocentrism: Review, Reconceptualization, and Empirical Testing. *Journal of International Marketing*. 23. 150305080544008. 10.1509/jim.14.0085.
- [30]. Spears, Nancy & Singh, Surendra. (2004). Measuring Attitude Toward the Brand and Purchase Intentions. *Journal of Current Issues and Research in Advertising*. 26. 53-66. 10.1080/10641734.2004.10505164.
- [31]. Steiner, B., & Brandhoff, M. (2020). An analysis of configurations of relationship quality dimensions to explain sources of behavioral outcomes in globalized manufacturing. *European Journal of Marketing*, 55(13), 1–40. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EJM-10-2018-0703>
- [32]. Sukhu, A., Scharff, R. (2016). Will ‘doing right’ lead to ‘doing well’? An examination of green behavior. *Journal of consumer marketing*, 35(2), 169-182.
- [33]. Sulhaini, S., & Herman Mulyono, L. E. (2014). The Effect of Ethnocentrism and Image of Asian Industrialised Countries on Perceived Relative Quality. *International Research Journal of Business Studies*, 7(3), 165–177. <https://doi.org/10.21632/irjbs.7.3.165-177>
- [34]. Thongkruer, P. ., & Wanarat, S. (2020). The mediating role of trust in the leading premium cosmetic clinics in Bangkok: The relationship of the media, trust, and beauty enhancement repurchasing. *Kasetsart Journal of Social Sciences*, 41(3), 659–664. Retrieved from <https://so04.tci-thaijo.org/index.php/kjss/article/view/247669>
- [35]. Tjiptono, Fandy. 2005. Strategi Pemasaran I. Edisi Kedua. Yogyakarta: Andi Offset.
- [36]. Tjiptono, F. Dan M.Craig-Less. 2004. Determinants of Local Brands Survival: A Proposed Framework. Proceeding of ANZMAC 2004 conference: Marketing Accountabilities and Responsibilities, Victoria University of Wellington, Wellington, New Zealand, 29 November-1 December
- [37]. Udayani, N. P. A., Wardana, M., & Giantari, I. G. A. K. (2018). Pengaruh consumer ethnocentrism terhadap country of origin dan purchase intention kosmetik lokaldi Denpasar. *Jurnal Administrasi Bisnis*, 8(1), 21-47.
- [38]. Widjaja, Y. R., Alamsyah, D. P., Rohaeni, H., & Sukajie, B. (2018). Peranan Kompetensi SDM UMKM dalam Meningkatkan Kinerja UMKM Desa Cilayung Kecamatan Jatinangor, Sumedang. *Jurnal*
- [39]. Wijaya, Z. P & Sanusi, F. D. (2021). Pengaruh Customer Experience, Location dan Product Diversity Terhadap Repurchase Intention. *Cakrawala Repositori IMWI*, 4(2), 207-217. <https://doi.org/10.52851/cakrawala.v4i2.86>
- [40]. Yani, A. M., Ikramuddin, Rusydi, Edyansyah. T. (2022). Pengaruh Variabel Consumer Nostalgic, Consumer Ethnocentrism, Dan Citra Merek Terhadap Minat Beli Konsumen Pada Produk Pepsodent. *Jurnal Visioner & Strategis*, 11(2).
- [41]. Yulianti, Y., & Keni, K. (2022). *Source Credibility, Perceived Quality, and Attitude Towards Brand as Predictor on Purchase Intention of Local Beauty Products: Tenth International Conference on Entrepreneurship and Business Management 2021 (ICEBM 2021)*, Jakarta, Indonesia. <https://doi.org/10.2991/aebmr.k.220501.074>
- [42]. Zeithaml, Valerie A, dan Bitner. 2000. *Service Marketing 2nd edition : Integrating Customer Focus*, New York : Mc Graw Hill Inc.
- [43]. Zeithaml, V. A. 1998. “Consumer Perception of Price, Quality, and Value: A Means-End Model and Synthesis of Evidence”. *Journal of Marketing*, Vol 52.